

Comments regarding the drift capacity values currently given in chapter 14 and the partial safety factor to be used in displacement-based verification.

V3.0, 20/11/2024, by G. Magenes (updated version of the document drafted on 20/4/2024, based on input from K.Beyer and P.Morandi).

1. General

The current values reported in table 14.4 (capacity at SD) are

Table 14.4— Unreinforced masonry: deformation capacities for piers or walls failing in shear. Applicable for axial load ratios $v_{EK} \leq 0,3$

Masonry type	Drift limits at SD [%]
Clay units, Gr 2	0,30
Clay units, Gr 1s	0,68
Calcium silicate (hollow and solid)	0,28
AAC Gr 1 and 1s	0,38
Light-weight concrete units, Gr 1	0,30

The above values are defined in BGDs [1, 2] as a 50% percentile for SD, accounting for a $R_{LH,SD}=1.1$ (loading history coefficient) and a $R_{ALF/NC}=1.2$ (axial load failure/20% force decay coefficient). The values given correspond to double-fixed boundary condition, not accounting for the H_0/H effect (BGD [1] page 5). In the same BGD document the average ratio between the 50% and 5 % percentile is estimated as 1.75. The values given in BGD [1,2] have also been used as the start point for the estimation of the q_D factors reported in table 14.1, accounting for a reduction factor = 1.75 (approximate 50%/5% percentile ratio). The q_D factors have been therefore evaluated assuming a safe estimate of the deformation capacity.

According to §14.6.2.3 (for SD) and §14.6.2.4 (for NC), the partial safety factor γ_{Rd} is to be applied to the displacement on the capacity curve of the building corresponding to the point at which a primary wall first reaches its resistance in terms of generalised in-plane deformations, that currently for URM is the member chord rotation given in Table 14.4. It can be assumed that the application of the partial factor to the displacement capacity on the pushover curve is approximately equivalent to the application of the partial factor to the deformation capacity of the individual walls, however it should be taken into consideration that in a real building, the h_0/h ratio in the critical walls is never as low as 0.5 (corresponding to the ideal double-fixed condition from which the values in Table 14.1 are given) but larger. Considering that the design displacement capacity will be obtained dividing the displacement corresponding to the attainment of the drift capacity in any primary wall by a partial safety factor γ_{Rd} in the order of 1.5-2 (see below), to neglect the H_0/H ratio effect will lead to an

unrealistically low design displacement capacity in displacement-based verification. It is therefore suggested that 14.9.2 is modified as follows

14.9.2 Unreinforced masonry members

(1) $\theta_{u2,SD}$ of walls failing in shear should be taken as a) or b):

a) the value given in Table 14.4 multiplied by $1.5 h_0/h$ (or $2h_0/h$) ≥ 1.0 , for axial load ratios $v_{E,k} \leq 0,3$;

b) the value given in ~~Table 14.4 a~~ multiplied by $(0.8 - v_{E,k}) \leq 0$ or the deformation capacity at the elastic limit for axial load ratios $v_{E,k} > 0,3$, whichever is greater.

Where

h_0 is the distance between the section with the largest in-plane bending moment in the wall and the contraflexure point;

h is the distance between the two extreme sections (top and bottom) sections of the wall element;

$v_{E,k}$ is the wall axial load ratio calculated as $v_{E,k} = N_{Ed}/(A_p f_k)$;

N_{Ed} is the axial force in the seismic design situation;

A_p is the wall section area as given in 14.4.1.2(4);

f_k is the characteristic compressive strength of the masonry wall.

Such effect of the h_0/h ratio will be reflected, as a consequence, also in the NC since the capacity at NC is related to SD via the product of a scalar coefficient.

After the check on two case study buildings [6] and on the basis of further data recently become available and analyses by C. Butenweg and discussed in the WG1 meetings, the choice of the coefficient $1.5 h_0/h$ (rather than $2.0 h_0/h$) is preferable to avoid overestimation of drift capacities at normalized axial ratios close to 0.2-0.3.

As regards the drift values currently given in table 14.1 it should be considered that the striking difference between the deformation capacity of walls made of clay units, Group 1, and the remaining units is in essence due to the way in which the ultimate chord rotation capacity has been evaluated from cyclic tests in BGD [2], i.e. the maximum absolute value between positive and negative loading direction. In the set of tests on walls made of clay units, Group 1, many tests showed a great difference in chord rotation at 20% force decay, if measured separately on the positive and negative envelope curve, making the definition of the chord rotation capacity very sensitive to how the positive and negative direction values are used. With such data, the criterion based on the maximum absolute value generates a dramatic increase in capacity and a larger c.o.v., compared to a criterion based on the mean or the minimum absolute value, and this can explain the large discrepancy with the other sets of wall types. Such excessively high chord rotation capacity would also produce an unrealistically high q_D factor for the case of clay units Gr.1, which was already not considered realistic and consistent with values given in EC8 for buildings made with other technologies such as reinforced concrete, and had to be reduced already, as proposed in BGD [1].

It is therefore suggested that for such group of units the mean chord rotation capacity with $h_0/h = 0.5$ is reduced from 0.68 to 0.45, which is however larger than the other masonry typologies and closer but

nevertheless larger than the value obtained by other authors (Morandi et al. [3,4]) considering the criterion based on the minimum absolute value.

The 50% percentile of chord rotation capacities at SD taken as a starpoint for the calibration of the table values and the partial safety factor would be therefore:

Table 1: proposed chord rotation capacity at SD, 50th percentile

Masonry type	θ at SD, 50th percentile [%]
Clay units, Gr 2	0.3
Clay units, Gr 1s	0.45
Calcium silicate (hollow and solid)	0.28
AAC Gr 1 and 1s	0.38
Light-weight concrete units, Gr 1	0.3

2. Partial safety factors and design values

According to the safety format set in the code, the design displacement capacity of the building will be obtained dividing the displacement corresponding to the attainment of the drift capacity in any primary wall by a partial safety factor γ_{Rd} , as per §14.6.2.3 (for SD) and §14.6.2.4 for NC.

It can be assumed in first instance that the application of the partial factor to the displacement capacity on the pushover curve is approximately equivalent to the application of the partial factor to the deformation capacity of the individual walls. The partial factor can therefore be obtained from the dispersion of the wall chord rotation capacities. By this assumption, the following relationships between the standard deviation of the deformation capacity and the γ_{Rd} factor are considered (Franchin [5]):

$$\gamma_{Rd,SD} = \exp(0.85 \cdot 1.6 \cdot \sigma_{lnR}) \quad \text{at SD} \quad (1)$$

$$\gamma_{Rd,NC} = \exp(0.85 \cdot 2.33 \cdot \sigma_{lnR}) \quad \text{at NC} \quad (2)$$

Where the coefficients 1.6 and 2.33 are associated to the accepted annual probability of exceedance and associated return period of the seismic action, respectively at SD and NC limit state and R is intended as the resistance parameter (in our case the chord rotation capacity θ)

By assuming that $\theta_{SD} = 0.75 \theta_{NC}$ the same σ_{lnR} can be assumed for SD and NC.

Using equations (1) and (2), the database on which the BGDs [1] and [2] were based provides the following values for the parameter γ_{Rd} of interest:

Table 2: partial factors for displacement based verification according to [2]

Masonry type	$\gamma_{RD,SD}$	$\gamma_{RD,NC}$
Clay units, Gr 2	1.51	1.82
Clay units, Gr 1s	1.64	2.05
Calcium silicate (hollow and solid)	1.87	2.49
AAC Gr 1 and 1s	1.70	2.17
Light-weight concrete units, Gr 1	n..a	n.a

where the value for light-weight concrete cannot be quantified because the number of test available is not sufficient to quantify the standard deviation.

The database used by Morandi et al. which is based in great part on the same data as [2], but where the chord rotation capacity at 20% force drop is evaluated using the criterion of the minimum absolute value between positive and negative loading direction, gives the following values:

Table 3: partial factors for displacement based verification according to [2]

Masonry type	$\gamma_{RD,SD}$	$\gamma_{RD,NC}$
Clay units, Gr 2	1.52	1.84
Clay units, Gr 1s	1.57	1.93
Calcium silicate (hollow and solid)	1.68	2.13
AAC Gr 1 and 1s	1.64	2.06
Light-weight concrete units, Gr 1	n..a	n.a

It is interesting to notice that for the typology on which the number of specimens is the largest (Clay units, Gr.2, 41 or 40 specimens in the two databases, respectively), the standard deviation and hence the partial factors are almost identical for the two databases, and are also smaller than for the other typologies that are characterized by a smaller number of tests. At the same time, for the other typologies with smaller number of tests, the standard deviation and the partial factors seem to be more affected by the use of different databases and criteria.

By applying the γ_{Rd} values of Table 2 to the chord rotation capacities of Table 1, the following “design values” for the chord rotation capacity at SD would result:

Table 4: design values of chord rotation at SD according to Table 1 and Table 2.

Masonry type	θ at SD, 50th percentile [%]	$\gamma_{RD,SD}$	$\theta_{SD}/\gamma_{RD,SD}$
Clay units, Gr 2	0.3	1.51	0.20
Clay units, Gr 1s	0.45	1.64	0.27
Calcium silicate (hollow and solid)	0.28	1.87	0.15
AAC Gr 1 and 1s	0.38	1.70	0.22
Light-weight concrete units, Gr 1	0.3	2.00	0.15

In the above calculation a partial safety factor of 2.00 has been set for light-weight concrete units, where data are insufficient to calculate the standard deviation. The last column of table 4 shows the “design values” of chord rotation capacity for each typology. If it appears impractical to use a different partial safety factor for each masonry typology, a reasonable approach could be to set a single value for $\gamma_{Rd,SD}$, (e.g. 1.7) correcting however the chord rotation capacity at 50th percentile (i.e. the values to be provided in table 14.4) , so that, when divided by the partial factor, the design values in the last column of Table 4 would be obtained.

Following this approach, and assuming a $\gamma_{Rd,SD} = 1.7$ for all typologies, the corrected values of chord rotation capacity would be as in the last column of the following table.

Table 5: corrected chord rotation capacities at SD to be used with $\gamma_{Rd,SD} = 1.7$ for all typologies at SD according to Table 4.

Masonry type	θ at SD, 50th percentile [%]	$\gamma_{RD,SD}$	$\theta_{SD}/\gamma_{RD,SD}$	$\theta_{SD\ corr}$
Clay units, Gr 2	0.3	1.51	0.20	0.34
Clay units, Gr 1s	0.45	1.64	0.27	0.47
Calcium silicate (hollow and solid)	0.28	1.87	0.15	0.25
AAC Gr 1 and 1s	0.38	1.70	0.22	0.38
Light-weight concrete units, Gr 1	0.3	2.00	0.15	0.26

For the NC verification, similar criteria are followed as above, accounting for the fact that the capacity at NC as per §14.9.2 is 1.5 times the capacity at SD (from BGD [1]). The following table is then obtained for the partial safety factors, design chord rotations at NC, and for the corrected chord rotation capacities at :

Table 6: corrected chord rotation capacities at NC to be used with $\gamma_{Rd,NC} = 2.1$ for all typologies at NC.

Masonry type	θ at NC, 50th percentile [%]	$\gamma_{RD,NC}$	$\theta_{NC}/\gamma_{RD,NC}$	$\theta_{NC\ corr}$
Clay units, Gr 2	0.45	1.82	0.25	0.52
Clay units, Gr 1s	0.68	2.05	0.33	0.69
Calcium silicate (hollow and solid)	0.42	2.49	0.17	0.35
AAC Gr 1 and 1s	0.57	2.17	0.26	0.55
Light-weight concrete units, Gr 1	0.45	2.60	0.17	0.36

The above result show that **the design values of deformation capacity at NC are only slightly** (approximately from 13 to 24%) **higher than the design values of deformation capacity at SD**. This is a consequence of the fact that it is assumed that $\theta_{NC} = 1.5 \theta_{SD}$ whereas from equations (1) and (2) the ratio $\frac{\gamma_{Rd,NC}}{\gamma_{Rd,SD}}$ ranges from 1.2 to 1.3. **This implies that the safety verification at SD will not necessarily guarantee the satisfaction of the safety verification at NC, since the displacement demand at NC will be always significantly larger than 1.13-1.24 times the demand at SD.** As an example, assuming as per the Italian NTC2018, $T_R = 475$ years for SD and $T_R = 975$ for NC, the ratio of the displacement demands for the elastic response spectrum at NC and SD ranges approximately from 1.7 to 1.25 for natural periods ranging fro $0.2T_c$ to T_c (the ratio of the displacement demand is higher the lower is the q^* demand at SD), according to Fajfar’s rule.

This outcome is not unexpected and makes sense on the basis of the experimental data and the way in which they were processed, but implies that if the displacement-based verification is carried out, then it should be carried out for both SD and NC.

Just for further information, if the γ_{Rd} factors evaluated from the database by Morandi et al. were used (which however produce also slightly different, lower, median values from the values given in BGD [1] and [2]) the following results would be obtained:

Table 7: “design” values and corrected chord rotation capacities at SD to be used with $\gamma_{RD,SD} = 1.7$ for all typologies at SD using standard deviations from Morandi et al..

Masonry type	θ at SD, 50th percentile [%]	$\gamma_{RD,SD}$	$\theta_{SD}/\gamma_{RD,SD}$	$\theta_{SD\ corr}$
Clay units, Gr 2	0.3	1.52	0.20	0.34
Clay units, Gr 1s	0.45	1.57	0.29	0.49
Calcium silicate (hollow and solid)	0.28	1.68	0.17	0.28
AAC Gr 1 and 1s	0.38	1.64	0.23	0.39
Light-weight concrete units, Gr 1	0.3	1.80	0.17	0.28

Table 8: “design” values and corrected chord rotation capacities at NC to be used with $\gamma_{RD,NC} = 2.1$ for all typologies at NC using standard deviations from Morandi et al..

Masonry type	θ at NC, 50th percentile [%]	$\gamma_{RD,NC}$	$\theta_{NC}/\gamma_{RD,NC}$	$\theta_{NC\ corr}$
Clay units, Gr 2	0.45	1.84	0.24	0.51
Clay units, Gr 1s	0.68	1.93	0.35	0.74
Calcium silicate (hollow and solid)	0.42	2.13	0.20	0.41
AAC Gr 1 and 1s	0.57	2.06	0.28	0.58
Light-weight concrete units, Gr 1	0.45	2.25	0.20	0.42

As expected, the values for Clay units Gr.2 remain essentially unchanged, whereas a slight increase of design values for the other typologies is found, and the design values of deformation capacity at NC are from 18% to 24% higher than the design values of deformation capacity at SD. The overall consequences regarding the relationship between SD verification and NC verification also remain substantially unchanged.

Since the idea of using one single safety coefficient for all the masonry typologies may be criticised from the conceptual point of view, because there is indeed a different degree of uncertainty for the different typologies due to the different number of tests available, a possible viable alternative could be to use two or three values total, for instance at SD 1.5 (clay Gr 2 and 3), 1.7 or 1.75 (all the rest with the exception of LWCU) and 2.0 for LWCU, with only minor adjustment to the median values, and maintaining visible (in the view of the NAD documents) the fact that there is indeed a different level of uncertainty that depends on the number of tests available (which can be improved as further tests become available). Similarly, possible values at NC could be 1.8 (clay Gr 2 and 3), 2.1 or 2.2 (all the rest with the exception of LWCU) and 2.6 for LWCU.

3. Updates based on additional data not previously included in databases [2] and [3]

Considering additional data recently provided in [7], and considering that there is no time to re-run the statistical analyses for the partial safety, WG1 proposes to round-up the 50th percentile of the drift capacity at SD for walls made of Calcium silicate units from 0.28% to 0.30%, keeping however the same values for the gamma factors derived in the previous section of this document. Regarding LWCU units, the additional data provided in [7] do not seem to show a much larger scatter compared to Calcium Silicate units or AAC units, hence the adoption of the same γ_{RD} factors could be reasonable, in view of further statistical processing.

References

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